

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #9

Sustainable Bioenergy and Side Bio-products Production on Coastal Urban Areas

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Executive Summary

Figure 9.1. Sustainable Bioenergy and Side bio-products Production on coastal urban areas - Graphical Abstract

This case study investigates industrial symbiosis in the biogas context in a coastal urban area of the Swedish west coast. The aim is to involve various stakeholders to develop the full potential of the biogas market and identify suitable forms of collaboration, figure 9.1. In conclusion, to

ensure the success of the biogas system, it is crucial to create a regional strategy involving key stakeholders and emulate successful examples from other areas while generating market demand through infrastructure and facilitation programs.

Abstract

Biogas production and utilization is a circular system that can contribute to bioenergy supply and climate transition. The biogas system however needs to involve industrial actors and other organizations in order to develop the full potential of the biogas market.

This case study will use the coastal urban area of the Swedish west coast to investigate drivers and barriers to industrial symbiosis in a biogas context, and to identify suitable forms for stakeholder collaboration. The aim is to identify the actors, their roles

and current and potential interactions within the system of industrial symbiosis. While doing so, business partners will be involved from different parts of the value chain that has an interest in developing the biogas market, sustainable business models, and industrial symbiosis. Side bio-products production using for instance the digestate as fertilizer or as basis for other products will be explored. Outcome of these activities in collaboration will be more circular solutions in society and more biogas substituting natural gas.

Introduction

The circular economy aligns with the overarching idea of sustainable development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the needs of future generations (Korhonen et al., 2018). The main areas and activities of the circular economy include the 5 R's: reuse, repair, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and

recycling to address the overarching aim of creating a closed-loop system that minimizes the use of resource inputs and the creation of waste (Maranesi & De Giovanni, 2020). According to Vanhamäki et al. (2020), a systematic change where local and regional actors play a central role is required to enable a transition to a circular economy. More specifically, broad cooperation among stakeholders such as municipalities, authorities, companies, and academia could facilitate sustainability-oriented investments and create business opportunities that originate from the perspective of circularity and resource efficiency. Biogas is a renewable and regionally produced fuel based on anaerobic digestion of biomass. Biogas systems have the potential to reduce methane emissions from waste like manure and food residues and at the same time the biogas produced can substitute for fossil fuels. Biogas can be utilized for heat, electricity, vehicle fuel production or as raw material in industry. Biogas

plants constitute promising future energy supply systems in which demand-driven electricity can be provided to compensate for mismatches between energy demand and supply from unpredictable sources such as wind and solar power (Mauky et al., 2017). Moreover, biogas technology has a small carbon footprint and has a low lifecycle greenhouse gas emission compared to other biofuels (Uusitalo et al., 2014).

Biogas closes loops and contributes to an economy where waste and residuals become valuable resources, such as climate-friendly biogas, biomethane and biofertilizer (Swedish Gas Association, 2021). In Europe, the demand for biogas has recently increased due to the possibility of substituting natural gas with biogas. Moreover, it has been shown that biogas solutions can contribute to all 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals which indicates that biogas solutions need to be studied and understood in a

broad, cross-sectoral system perspective (Hagman & Eklund, 2016).

Sweden has increased biogas use dramatically since 2015 but the increase is mostly due to the import of biogas from Denmark. An increase of Swedish biogas production up to 10 TWh until 2030 has been suggested (Biogasmarknadsutredningen, 2019) and new policy instruments have been introduced. Of the biogas produced in Sweden most (64 %) is upgraded and used for road transport due to favourable financial support systems. The market for biomethane as a transportation fuel is now rather developed in Sweden but is highly dependent on increased policy incentives and long-term support systems to take the next step (Klackenberg, 2023). Biogas is also in demand by industry as a fuel and raw material for a range of industrial purposes such as plastic, paint and lubricants (International Gas Union, 2015).

Biogas production is considered

to contribute to a green, local economy that provides job opportunities and secures nutrient cycling. Although many benefits can be gained from biogas production Swedish actors have been struggling with low profitability and the development has reached a stagnation. There are however still many actors that want to develop their activities and existing business models by developing new business concepts aimed at future biogas expansion and thus contributing to the climate transition. A way forward for these actors could be more long-term subsidies and subsidies linked to regional biogas development objectives (Niskanen & Magnusson, 2021) but also more cooperation between different local businesses in industrial symbiosis. In a collaboration model, stakeholders are independent and interdependent in their interactions. They create norms, rules, and structures for how to act and how to achieve collaborations based

on mutually beneficial interactions. Collaboration models expect to bring through achievements that otherwise may not have been obtained (Knudsen, 2007) and enable organizations to collectively manage risks and take advantage of potentials, e.g., facilitate market launch, gain access to new markets and offer mechanisms to avoid potential market failures (Laperche & Liu, 2013). For example, customers may contribute with new ideas and solutions, improve design, provide information on market trends, and identification of market opportunities (Nieto & Santamaría, 2007).

Suppliers may for instance identify new methods, and technical or design problems and contribute to the successful launch of new efficient solutions (Jean et al., 2014). Thus, the aim of collaboration models also includes establishing a culture where citizens become active parts of the development.

The overarching aim of this case study is to develop a framework

that can support the establishment of industrial symbiosis based on biogas production where the supply and demand of biogas and its bioproducts can be increased and matched.

Description of Case Study

The case study has been structured into three parts that build on each other in order to meet the aim. These are all part of a process that will initially create a benchmark for the possibilities of increased biogas production and utilization in symbiosis with other actors in the value chain, develop a conceptual roadmap of how such industrial symbiosis could be arranged, and provide further understanding of how the industrial symbiosis based on biogas production could be established and managed through collaboration models and a knowledge base for a prototype. Such a prototype will ease the dissemination, communication, and application of the case study results.

After this work has finished the prototype can serve as inspiration and encourage actors to start collaborating and building industrial symbiosis networks.

Case Study Solution

The main idea of industrial symbiosis (IS) is to create synergies; one business's waste becomes another business's feedstock in order to improve resource efficiency. In the district energy industry in Sweden, there are many examples of industrial symbioses where partners need to understand each other's processes and value drivers (Thollander et al., 2010; Walsh & Thornley, 2012). The case study will investigate motivations, dynamics, interactions and governance, which are important aspects for facilitating and maintaining the synergies (Martin, 2020). Industrial symbiosis can contribute to a secured energy supply as well as lead to more robust businesses contributing additional job opportunities within the green sector giving a positive and sustainable impact on the communities that the symbiosis acts within.

However, knowledge of practical industrial symbiosis cases which will contribute to a renewable, robust, and flexible energy system is treating and refining biological streams (e.g., the biogas process) remains underexplored, and a more in-depth understanding of opportunities and challenges presented by industrial symbiosis is needed to advance its applicability (Vanhamäki et al., 2020).

The methodology of the case study will be first a literature study to increase the knowledge of the concept of industrial symbiosis and to establish a benchmark for understanding needs and challenges in connection to industrial symbiosis in general and also in the biogas context. Interviews will be performed with different stakeholders that could be involved in an industrial symbiosis.

There is also a need for a deeper understanding of how current and potential stakeholders, critical for the establishment of biogas

industrial symbiosis can be involved in the development process. Research has shown that biogas producers and users need to innovate not just the biogas product and attached services but also collaboration and business models and that successful dissemination and adoption of biogas typically requires the transformation of processes, business activities and organizations (Karlsson et al., 2019). Collaboration models (in which businesses cooperate with each other and/or stakeholders to jointly explore e.g., knowledge transfer and new business opportunities) may be specifically critical in cases such as the biogas market with many small, separated stakeholders, with limited resources and with difficulties to have capacity and channels for commercialization. Currently, we identify a lack of a unified conceptualization of collaboration models (K. Blomqvist & Levy, 2006). We need to know more about challenges in the

development of collaboration models in the context of biogas production and how to overcome such challenges. Moreover, It is also relevant to explore the collaboration models, their fundamental cornerstones and their orchestration, particularly in the context of biogas industrial symbiosis and viable business models. The field of collaboration models has so far been neglected in the biogas area and studies like this are needed to bring forth collaboration for early-stage innovative products and services in the biogas market in order to develop viable offerings to the multiple key stakeholders. In this, the stakeholder's ability and willingness to take part in the exchange and to commit to the collaboration are in previous studies identified as critical (Knudsen, 2007). One key example is collaboration with regard to sustainable business model transformation.

To accelerate the commercialization and adoption of biogas and for the potential industrial symbiosis to be developed the case study will create roadmaps based on collaborative processes actively involving practitioners as key stakeholders to incorporate different skills, resources, market aspects and societal needs. Identification of a biogas-business-industrial symbiosis-fit will be an iterative process where the research team and the partners co-create and align their views and understanding of both possibilities and limitations but also how to overcome hurdles.

The results will be made available and useful for many different actors and develop recommendations for measures that can promote the development of industrial symbioses with a biogas context. In the long run, this should lead to more biogas plants being established and more actors being involved.

The results have a direct impact on several important target groups:

- actors who intend to build new biogas plants
- actors who can use the biogas or biofertilizer in production or processes
- actors who can otherwise be linked to the industrial symbiosis
- government officials
- the public interested in biogas

These target groups are directly involved in the project and develop increased knowledge and new perspectives through participation in interviews. In the closing workshop, other target groups also have opportunities to directly influence the recommendations that are highlighted as results. Target groups here are the entire biogas industry, and also county administrations and municipalities.

Results and Discussion

The practice of utilising by-products and residual energy from industrial and urban processes is not a new practice. However, it appears that many opportunities still exist to be exploited but have not been developed for various reasons. One of the

key reasons are due to the lack of a facilitation programme that increases awareness and knowledge flows, as well as a lack of specific policy incentives.

The generic Roadmap for IS in Sweden (Harris et al., 2018) was developed to highlight key components and actions needed to enable the identification, development and realisation of industrial symbiosis exchanges between partners. The Roadmap is focused on five critical elements and actions:

1. Create a systematic facilitation programme - Regional Centres supported by a National Centre.
2. Establish support mechanisms – including Task Forces that provide supporting knowledge in key areas, (e.g. recovery technology) and drive forward key issues; as well as research in key areas.

3. Generate market demand – e.g. through awareness activities, as well as local and national government procurement.

4. Develop policy drivers - for industrial symbiosis whilst improving the overall policy environment by removing barriers.

5. Align IS across different sectors and approaches – this refers primarily to fostering IS across the key pillars of society urban areas, industrial and agriculture and forestry; as well as aligning sectorial policies to ensure IS can flourish

In the biogas context a report was developed with 2 different scenarios discussing how biogas production can be increased through industrial symbiosis (Symbiosis Center Denmark, 2019). The cases from Denmark could show that there are possibilities but also barriers in terms of technical or legal barriers but also the need

for investments can be an essential barrier to the establishment of green industrial symbiosis with the utilisation of biogas. The uncertain prospects for the framework conditions for production, sales and use of biogas reduce the willingness to invest in both biogas plants and biogas processing plants (Symbiosis Center Denmark, 2019).

In the coastal urban area of the Swedish west coast there are several cases of industrial symbiosis recently started or already developed with biogas as a key component.

- In Vessige Biogas there are about 30 members in a cooperative with several big animal farms producing manure and other kinds of substrates for the biogas production but also working with other, upgrading to biomethane, using the biofertilizer and running a gas station. The biogas is used for heating, electricity, input on the

gas grid and as fuel for cars, tractors, and heavy vehicles. The municipality in which the cooperative is situated, Falkenberg municipality is important in permit processes and have an interest in the development of Vessige biogas since the municipality vehicles can use the biomethane and since it creates business opportunities, facilitate the fulfillment of climate goals and contribute to rural development in the municipality. The University researchers have investigated what motivations and obstacles there are for developing industrial symbiosis and what policy evolution and behavioral change could possibly drive a positive development of biogas production in the agricultural sector. In order to be able to make these investments Vessige biogas cooperative have received governmental support (Klimatklivet) distributed via the Swedish environmental protection agency and through that

been able to start the development of an industrial symbiosis.

- Sotenäs Symbiocenter currently has an industrial symbiosis network where several actors collaborate with the sea as a starting point. The symbiosis network started its development in 2011 and today it operates a privately owned biogas plant (Renahav) as a connecting hub for resource exchanges between sea and land. With more companies in the blue industry being established in Sotenäs, the network will be further developed and opportunities for new synergic effects created. At the same time, several companies in the network want to review side streams for better resource utilization. Through collaboration between academia, authorities, public and private sector, the industrial symbiosis will contribute to higher

knowledge and competence for the use of resources and energy from the food industry, agriculture and aquaculture, e.g. through product processing and biogas production.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In order to establish an industrial symbiosis in the biogas context there has to be networks of different stakeholders that are interested in collaboration and increasing the biogas production and use of biogas, biomethane and biofertilizer. Recommendations for further

development of industrial symbiosis in the biogas sector are to:

- Create a regional strategy for the development of the biogas system together with key stakeholders and local politicians
- Create meeting points and communicate IS among companies, farmers, consultants, municipalities and academia
- Mimic the good examples from other areas
- Start facilitation programs to support initiatives from the beginning
- Generate market demand through infrastructure and procurements

There must also be continuous learning and activities such as workshops, study visits and sharing of knowledge. With this a successful development of industrial symbiosis in the biogas context can be realized.

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